

With the original command line arguments as used in the paper. The dynamic chunksize sets at 128K events per processing task, for a target memory consumption per task of 2GB:



Using the command line switch `--do-systs` to add systematic uncertainty tracking. Number of splits increases, and the dynamic chunksize sets at 16K events per processing task, for a target memory consumption per task of 2GB.

